

PERITONEAL PLASMA CELL NEOPLASM MIMICKING TUBERCULOUS PERITONITIS AND COMPLICATED BY COLONIC PERFORATION

TÜBERKÜLOZ PERİTONİTİNİ TAKLİT EDEN VE KOLON PERFORASYONU İLE KOMPLİKE OLAN PERİTONEL PLAZMA HÜCRELİ NEOPLAZM

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ABSTRACT

Case: A 53-year-old man with diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and end-stage renal disease on hemodialysis presented with abdominal pain, bloating, and diarrhea. Abdominal computed tomography demonstrated massive ascites, diffuse peritoneal thickening, and lymphadenopathies. Ascitic fluid analysis revealed low-SAAG lymphocyte-predominant exudative ascites with markedly elevated ADA and low glucose levels, strongly mimicking tuberculous peritonitis. However, microbiological studies were negative, and diagnostic laparoscopy with peritoneal biopsy demonstrated plasma cell neoplasia with lambda light-chain restriction. During follow-up, the patient developed spontaneous colonic perforation requiring emergency surgery. Histopathological examination of the colectomy specimen revealed diffuse plasma cell infiltration involving the bowel wall with transmural ischemic necrosis. The patient died postoperatively. This case highlights the diagnostic challenge of peritoneal plasma cell neoplasms, which may mimic tuberculous peritonitis clinically, radiologically, and biochemically, including markedly elevated ascitic ADA levels. Additionally, spontaneous colonic perforation due to bowel-wall plasma cell infiltration appears to be exceedingly rare.

Keywords: Ascites, Colonic perforation, Peritoneal involvement, Plasma cell neoplasms, Tuberculous peritonitis.

ÖZET

Vaka: Diyabet, hipertansiyon ve hemodiyaliz tedavisi gören son dönem böbrek yetmezliği olan 53 yaşında bir erkek hasta karın ağrısı, şişkinlik ve ishal şikayetleriyle başvurdu. Karın bilgisayar tomografisinde yaygın asit, diffüz periton kalınlaşması ve lenfadenopati saptandı. Asit sıvısı analizinde, belirgin şekilde yüksek ADA ve düşük glukoz seviyeleri ile birlikte düşük SAAG lenfosit ağırlıklı eksüdatif asit saptandı; bu durum tüberküloz peritonitini güçlü bir şekilde taklit ediyordu. Bununla birlikte, mikrobiyolojik incelemeler negatifti ve periton biyopsisi ile yapılan tanısal laparoskopide lambda hafif zincir kısıtlaması olan plazma hücreli neoplazi saptandı. Takip sırasında hastada spontan kolon perforasyonu gelişti ve acil cerrahi müdahale gerektirdi. Kolonektomi örneğinin histopatolojik incelemesinde, bağırsak duvarını etkileyen diffüz plazma hücre infiltrasyonu ve transmural iskemik nekroz saptandı. Hasta ameliyat sonrası dönemde hayatını kaybetti. Bu vaka, klinik, radyolojik ve biyokimyasal olarak, belirgin şekilde yüksek asit ADA düzeyleri de dahil olmak üzere, tüberküloz peritonitini taklit edebilen periton plazma hücreli neoplazmlarının tanısal zorluğunu vurgulamaktadır. Ayrıca, bağırsak duvarı plazma hücre infiltrasyonuna bağlı spontan kolon perforasyonu son derece nadir görünmektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Asites, Kolon perforasyonu, Periton tutulumu, Plazma hücreli neoplazmlar, Tüberküloz peritonit.

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INTRODUCTION

Peritoneal involvement of plasma cell neoplasms, often referred to as myelomatous ascites or peritoneal plasmacytosis, is exceptionally uncommon. Fewer than 1% of multiple myeloma patients develop myelomatous ascites, and even fewer present with peritoneal-only disease (Mitra et al. 2014). In most reported cases, patients with peritoneal plasmacytosis initially present with nonspecific abdominal symptoms and are often misdiagnosed as having tuberculous peritonitis or peritoneal carcinomatosis (Mitra et al. 2014; Choi et al. 2017). The pathophysiology of peritoneal involvement remains unclear, but it is thought that peritoneal involvement may occur via lymphatic or hematogenous routes. Analysis of ascites in these cases reveals high protein concentrations and lymphocyte predominance, thus resembling tuberculous and malignant ascites. Here, we present a fatal case characterized by exudative ascites and peritoneal thickening, highlighting the diagnostic challenges of distinguishing plasma cell neoplasms from infectious or malignant peritoneal diseases.

Patient Presentation

A 53-year-old male patient with type 2 diabetes, hypertension, and end-stage renal disease, who was on a routine three-day-a-week dialysis program, presented to the emergency department with complaints of abdominal pain, bloating, and diarrhea. Physical examination revealed tenderness in the epigastric region and shifting dullness consistent with ascites. A CT scan performed in the emergency department revealed massive ascites with diffuse peritoneal thickening, nodular peritoneal appearance, and multiple lymph nodes. Detailed ascitic fluid analysis revealed low-SAAG exudative ascites (serum albumin: 32.6 g/L; ascitic albumin: 27.91 g/L; SAAG: 0.47 g/dL) with lymphocyte predominance, markedly elevated LDH (5170 U/L), high total protein concentration (64.06 g/L), profoundly low glucose level (6 mg/dL), and markedly elevated ADA level (210.4 U/L). These findings strongly suggested tuberculous peritonitis. Tuberculous peritonitis was suspected, and the ascitic fluid was sent to the microbiology laboratory for examination for acid-fast bacilli. Due to persistent diarrhea, a colonoscopy was performed, but the patient's bowel preparation was suboptimal. Therefore, a colonoscopy limited to the splenic flexure revealed locally hyperemic, edematous, and exudate-covered mucosa in the rectum and sigmoid colon. Acid-fast bacilli examination from ascitic fluid was negative. Despite the markedly elevated ADA level and biochemical findings suggestive of tuberculous peritonitis, microbiological studies remained negative, and histopathological evaluation of peritoneal biopsy specimens did not demonstrate granulomatous inflammation or evidence of tuberculosis. Diagnostic laparoscopy and peritoneal biopsy were performed, confirming plasma cell infiltration consistent with extramedullary plasmacytoma (CD138 positive, lambda light chain-restricted).

Figure 1. Diagnostic laparoscopy demonstrating diffuse fibrotic thickening and nodular involvement of the peritoneal surfaces, highly suggestive of infiltrative peritoneal disease.

Figure 2. Contrast-enhanced abdominal CT scan showing massive ascites, diffuse irregular peritoneal thickening, nodular peritoneal enhancement, and multiple lymphadenopathies.

During follow-up, spontaneous colonic perforation developed, necessitating emergency subtotal colectomy with omentectomy. Histopathological examination of the surgical specimen demonstrated diffuse atypical plasma cell infiltration extending from the muscularis propria to the subserosal adipose tissue, accompanied by transmural ischemia, necrosis, ulceration, hemorrhage, and chronic active inflammation. Immunohistochemical analysis again showed CD138 and CD56 positivity with lambda light-chain restriction, supporting persistent monoclonal plasma cell neoplasia involving the bowel wall and peritoneal tissues. The patient, unfortunately, died postoperatively.

DISCUSSION

Peritoneal plasmacytosis, or myelomatous ascites, is a rare manifestation of plasma cell dyscrasias and generally carries a poor prognosis (Mitra et al. 2014). Although the pathophysiology of myelomatous ascites is not fully understood, it includes direct peritoneal infiltration of malignant plasma cells, lymphatic or hematogenous dissemination, and secondary seeding following serosal involvement. Increased vascular permeability and cytokine-mediated inflammation may also contribute to ascites formation (Kyle and Rajkumar, 2004). Diagnosing peritoneal plasmacytosis is frequently difficult, as both the clinical presentation and imaging findings can closely resemble more common conditions such as tuberculous peritonitis and peritoneal carcinomatosis. In the report by Choi et al., a significant portion of patients were treated for suspected tuberculosis before the diagnosis of plasma cell tumor was confirmed. Similarly, in our case, the presence of low-glucose, lymphocyte-predominant exudative ascites led to early diagnostic uncertainty. Interestingly, our patient also demonstrated markedly elevated ascitic ADA levels, which further increased clinical suspicion for tuberculous peritonitis. This finding is particularly noteworthy because elevated ADA levels are generally considered highly suggestive of tuberculous peritonitis. Therefore, our case highlights that peritoneal plasma cell neoplasms may mimic tuberculous peritonitis not only clinically and radiologically, but also biochemically. There is no accepted treatment algorithm for the management of peritoneal plasma cell neoplasms. Published cases have used systemic chemotherapy, corticosteroids, and ascites drainage. Despite these treatment strategies, overall clinical outcomes generally remain poor. The rapid deterioration and fatal progression observed in our patient further emphasize the aggressive and progressive nature of this disease. Although extremely rare, colonic perforation can potentially occur due to plasma cell infiltration through the bowel wall or ischemic changes resulting from disease-induced proliferative and inflammatory processes (Vaxman et al., 2020; Kitamura et al., 2018). In our patient, histopathological examination of the colectomy specimen demonstrated direct plasma cell infiltration extending through the bowel wall from the muscularis propria to the subserosal tissue, together with transmural ischemic necrosis and severe inflammatory changes. Unlike previously reported cases in the literature that were primarily associated with high-dose steroid therapy, our patient developed spontaneous perforation in the absence of steroid exposure, highlighting a distinct and potentially infiltration-driven mechanism of bowel

injury. To our knowledge, cases demonstrating both markedly elevated ascitic ADA levels and bowel-wall plasma cell infiltration leading to spontaneous colonic perforation are exceedingly rare.

This case adds valuable information to the limited literature on extramedullary peritoneal neoplasms and highlights the importance of maintaining a broad diagnostic perspective when evaluating atypical ascites that respond poorly to empiric therapy. Because comprehensive hematologic evaluation and bone marrow biopsy could not be completed before the patient's death, definitive distinction between plasma cell myeloma and solitary extramedullary plasmacytoma could not be established. Early biopsy and a collaborative multidisciplinary approach are vital to optimize patient outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In patients presenting with unexplained exudative ascites and peritoneal thickening, plasma cell neoplasms should be considered in the differential diagnosis. A multidisciplinary approach and avoidance of delays in diagnostic peritoneal biopsies may improve the patient's prognosis.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

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REFERENCES

- Choi SY, Lee SW, Jeong WK, et al. Myelomatous ascites as an initial manifestation of extramedullary involvement of multiple myeloma. *J Korean Soc Radiol.* 2017;76(3):187–191. doi:10.3348/jksr.2017.76.3.187
- Kitamura F, Iwamuro M, Shiraha H, et al. Primary extramedullary plasmacytoma of the sigmoid colon with perforation. *Int J Surg Case Rep.* 2018;46:1–4. doi:10.1016/j.ijscr.2018.03.022
- Kyle RA, Rajkumar SV. Multiple myeloma. *N Engl J Med.* 2004;351(18):1860–1873. doi:10.1056/NEJMra041875
- Mitra S, Bhattacharyya M, Bandyopadhyay R, Banerjee S, Ghosh A, et al. IgG lambda myeloma presenting as plasmacytic ascites. *Indian J Hematol Blood Transfus.* 2014;30(Suppl 1):451–454. doi:10.1007/s12288-014-0375-3
- Vaxman I, Al Saleh AS, Kumar S, Nitin M, Dispenzieri A, Buadi F, Dingli D, Lacy M, Muchtar E, Hobbs M, Fonder A, Hwa L, Visram A, Kapoor P, Siddiqui M, Lust J, Kyle R, Rajkumar V, Hayman S, Leung N, Gonsalves W, Kourelis T, Warsame R, Gertz MA. Colon perforation in multiple myeloma patients – A complication of high-dose steroid treatment. *Cancer Med.* 2020;9(23):8895–8901. doi:10.1002/cam4.3507